

REPORT

CONCEPT

Interim report

Pre-call trajectory Citizen Science

Commissioned by Open Science NL & NWA (both NWO – Dutch Research Council)

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Executive summary

This report examines the preconditions for equal partnerships between citizens and researchers in participatory research, with the aim of improving scientific knowledge, action or policy change. The research, conducted by TwynstraGudde on behalf of Open Science NL (NWO), summarises desk research and interviews with 15 experts from both the Netherlands and abroad. We analyse these results using our lens for equal partnership collaboration in which we distinguish between four aspects: **motivation, organisation, interaction and realisation**.

Motivation: Potentially, equal partnerships in participatory research can contribute to democratisation of science, better research outcomes and increased trust in science. Motivations for collaboration in participatory research vary widely. Motivations can range from egocentric and altruistic drives to more collectivist and principled ones. Timely recognition and appreciation of these motivations can help make collaboration sustainable.

Organisation: Successful collaboration requires a well-thought-out strategy, clear organisational structure and sufficient support and funding. Flexible and open funding programmes are essential to involve different participants in an equal manner. There is a need for supporting voluntary commitment and reimbursement of expenses for citizens, patients and other non-traditional stakeholders. Funders play a crucial role in creating innovative funding programmes and sharing knowledge on best practices.

Interaction: Equal partnership collaboration depends on expressed interests, valued differences and a sense of equality. Training and networking are crucial to strengthen these. It is important to overcome barriers arising from power differences and prejudices between different groups. Organising meetings, involving children, for example through approaching schools, and lowering the threshold for participation can all help to make collaboration more equal.

Realisation: The success of collaboration should be visible and meaningful, with attention to monitoring, reflection and adaptive capacity. It is important to celebrate results and recognise the added value of collaboration. Citizen science can contribute to better scientific outcomes, increased trust in science and social cohesion. Creating a learning process and space for experimenting with new forms of funding are essential for sustainable collaboration.

The report concludes that equal collaboration in participatory research requires attention to the specific points mentioned above. By addressing these aspects, NWO can contribute to sustainable and meaningful collaborations between citizens and researchers. This study offers several starting points for NWO to think about funding and supporting equal collaboration in participatory research. By better addressing the motivations of citizens and other non-traditional stakeholders and sharing influence in design and decision-making, NWO can contribute to more equal collaborations from the start of programmes and projects.

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1. Introduction

Citizen science and other participatory forms of research have a rich history and are developing rapidly both inside and outside of the Netherlands.¹² There are many definitions of citizen science. For this report, we define participatory research as **the active involvement of non-traditional stakeholders in research** in partnership/collaboration with scientists or professionals resulting in scientific knowledge, action (e.g. for conservation) or policy change. Non-traditional stakeholders can be divided into groups of citizens, citizen representatives, patient organisations, NGOs, private organisations, and public organisations such as municipalities.

The involvement of non-traditional stakeholders can be organised at **different stages** within research: from agenda setting and co-deciding on the terms of funding programmes (programming), to implementing concrete projects to achieve high-quality participatory research/citizen science.

A specific problem within participatory research is **unequal influence of and collaboration with non-traditional stakeholders**.³ Especially in lighter forms of citizen science, they are still too often seen as potential data points rather than full-fledged research partners. Often in research projects, academic researchers are in the lead. They set up the project and execute it. Involving non-traditional stakeholders such as citizens, citizen representatives, patient organisations, municipalities, etc., in research projects led by researchers can lead to misunderstanding and unequal influence. Often, non-traditional stakeholders do not feel like equal partners. Incidentally, this is a situation that does not only occur in consortia in which citizens participate. Even in consortia in which researchers from different domains, governments and civil society organisations, companies (e.g. public-private partnerships) work together, there are often unequal timelines, different use of concepts and unequal relationships that pose a challenge to collaborations.

Open Science NL and NWA (both NWO) asked TwynstraGudde to investigate under which preconditions citizens and other non-traditional stakeholders can collaborate on a more equal footing with researchers in research projects. This leads to the following main question:

Under which preconditions can citizens (organisations) and researchers collaborate in research projects in a (more) equal way?

Open Science NL has indicated to us that they are also interested in the question of what is needed in the development process of a funding programme: which stakeholders should be involved and what support is needed for this? Furthermore, Open Science NL wants to explore whether and how an innovative targeted funding programme for citizen science can be set up within NWO.

This first interim report presents the results of a desk study and the analysis of interviews with experience experts from the Netherlands and abroad. In the next chapter, we first outline the theoretical framework used. We then describe the methodology used. Next, we describe the results of the desk study and interviews. We conclude with some key insights and a look ahead.

¹ Dekker, T., Kuijpers, E., & Lenarduzzi, C. (2023). Van crowdsourcing naar echte burgerwetenschap: Invester in de kwaliteit van samenwerking. *Stadsgeschiedenis*, 18(2).

² Haklay, M., Dörler, D., Heigl, F., Manzoni, M., Hecker, S., & Vohland, K. (2021). What is citizen science? The challenges of definition. *The science of citizen science*.

³ Soleri, D., Long, J. W., Ramirez-Andreotta, M. D., Eitemiller, R., & Pandya, R. (2016). Finding pathways to more equitable and meaningful public-scientist partnerships. *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*. 1 (1): 9, 1(1).

Note: Open Science NL is working in close coordination with those involved in the National Science Agenda (NWA). A parallel process is also in progress to map how citizen science and citizen participation is already taking place within existing NWA-funded projects. Therefore, projects from the NWA have been excluded for this specific study.

2. Theoretical lens

To be able to make statements about preconditions for equal collaboration in participatory research, it is first important to establish what we mean by **equal** collaborations. For us, equality is about taking into account the identity and personal background of all those involved in such a way that they are able to participate. This is different from striving for complete equality.⁴ We also speak of the difference between equity and equality:

Equity is an approach that recognizes that the magnitude of systemic barriers posed to a particular person will vary based on their [background]. Equity recognizes that different people will need different amounts of resources or support in order to succeed and overcome these barriers. It is important to note that equity is different than equality, because equality-based approaches assume that everyone should be treated the same.⁵⁶

For the **preconditions** for equal collaboration, we use our lens to analyse the patterns. In doing so, we pay attention to four preconditions that require attention for equal partner collaborations.

⁴ <https://codedi.nl/inspiratie-tips/gelijkheid-versus-gelijkwaardigheid-hoe-verhouden-zich-tot-diversiteit-inclusie/>

⁵ <https://sparcopen.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/Diversity-Equity-and-Inclusion-Report-July-10-V1-Release.pdf>

⁶ See Minow, M. (2021). Equality vs. equity. *American Journal of Law and Equality*, 1, 167-193 for an elaborate and nuanced discussion of the various concepts, their histories and contemporary usage.

The motivation: why are we working together?

Why collaboration takes place can vary greatly. Scientific research and our own practical experiences show that it is very important to have an eye for what motivates the different partners. What motivates each partner to collaborate; what drives them? Is it clear what the aim of the collaboration is, and do the partners really depend on each other to achieve the goals? Success factors we distinguish here are the extent of: 1) the sense of urgency, 2) the shared ambitions, 3) clear defined goals and 4) the dependence on each other.

The organisation: how do we work together (structure/hard)?

Collaborations need to be organised. This is often quite difficult, as we see in practice. At the start of a collaboration, there is no plan, division of tasks, routines or procedures. The partners will have to develop these together and experience success together. Success factors we distinguish here are the extent to which there is: 1) a well-thought-out strategy and approach, 2) a clear organisational structure and decision-making, 3) sufficient resources and appropriate frameworks, and 4) involved parties.

The interaction: how do we work together (culture/soft)?

Besides factors relating to the more 'structural aspects' of organising a collaboration, success also depends on factors that are somewhat less 'visible'. Factors that relate to the way the people involved treat each other: the interaction. Success factors we distinguish here are the extent to which there are: 1) expressed interests, 2) valued differences, 3) a sense of equality and, 4) a powerful team.

The realisation: what does the collaboration deliver?

You collaborate for a reason: it needs to deliver something. Visible and jointly celebrated successes motivate partners to keep putting energy into the collaboration. It is therefore important to pay attention to the results and added value of the collaboration, and to keep track of this continually. Success factors we therefore distinguish are the extent to which there is: 1) monitoring and reflection, 2) adaptive capacity, 3) meaningful results, and 4) added value.

3. Methods

The main objective of this research is to advise on the preconditions under which citizens (organisations) and researchers can collaborate in research projects on a more equal footing. The decision-making and implementation of the final advice we will deliver is assigned to the Open Science NL/NWA Steering Committee and the NWO Executive Board.

For this first interim report, we performed a short **desk study** and conducted **in-depth interviews** with experts. For the desk study, we mapped publications from academia and policy that focus on ways to promote citizen science and other forms of participatory research and on ways to specifically organise mutual standing of citizens and researchers in citizen science.

For the interviews, we spoke to a total of 15 experts from the Netherlands and abroad. For instance, we spoke to experienced participatory researchers, citizen scientists, a participation expert, a concerned municipal official and an ethicist. We also spoke to programme managers of funding programmes for participatory research from the Netherlands and abroad (UK and Austria). See Appendix 1 for an anonymised list of interviewees.

Among other things, we asked them about their involvement in citizen science and participatory research, their ambitions and vision for it, and what goes well and less well on formal and informal organisation around participatory research. We also asked about suitable evaluation criteria for programmes and projects, about skills and expertise of members of evaluation committees, suitable lengths of funding programmes and trade-offs about the length of programmes and we also asked about suitable budget requirements and preconditions for funding participatory research.

We then coded the data we collected in a semi-open manner using the four main categories of our looking glass on equal collaboration. This way, we did not unnecessarily limit ourselves to existing success factors and left enough room for other perspectives.

In a subsequent workshop (social lab)⁷ with external participants, we will further deepen these results.⁸ The next report will address the results.

⁷ Marschalek, I., Blok, V., Bernstein, M., Braun, R., Cohen, J., Hofer, M., ... & Kumar Thapa, R. (2022). The social lab as a method for experimental engagement in participatory research. *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, 9(3), 419-442.

⁸ <https://www.openscience.nl/bijeenkomsten/gelijkwaardigheid-in-participatief-onderzoek-geef-je-op>

4. Results

4.1 Document study

In the next section, we discuss the results from the desk review. We will first consider what the current literature states about the status of the four preconditions in relation to citizen science and other forms of participatory research. After this section, we will map out recommendations from the literature on ways to promote (equality in) participatory research.

4.1.1 Motivation

Looking at **the motivation and specifically the goals** to which citizen science and other forms of participatory research should contribute, we see different perspectives in the literature.

Classically, collaboration between researchers and other non-traditional stakeholders in science can contribute to three different goals.^{9,10} First, there is the normative perspective that argues that such collaboration can lead to a democratisation of science. This is necessary from the normative perspective because people whose lives are affected by science should also be able to influence it. The second perspective sees substantive benefits of such collaboration, because it can contribute to better research outcomes. Finally, the third, instrumental perspective argues that cooperation between scientists and society can lead to increased trust in science and better policy impact of proposed measures.

Empirical research shows that human motives behind participation in citizen science projects, both on the side of scientists and volunteers exist. From ego-centric motives ("I can use the data to enrich my research"/"I can broaden my own horizons by participating in this") and altruism ("I can introduce other people to the scientific method through this collaboration"/"I can help scientists through this collaboration") to more collectivist ("this collaboration is good for my community") and principled motives ("this collaboration helps to open up knowledge for all").¹¹ Moreover, this study shows that these motives can change over time and are influenced by timing of recognition and appreciation, among others.

Other research shows that clashes may occur between parties: for instance, scientific goals of achieving results and the will to learn may be at odds, communication styles may clash, citizen-scientists may disagree with each other, and stakeholders may think differently about the relationship between science and activism.¹² Moreover, scientists may feel threatened in their autonomy of research and therefore be anxious to involve other kinds of actors in what they do.¹³ This is not beneficial to equality in collaborations.

⁹ Rathenau Instituut (2021). *Samen verder met open science – Op weg naar betekenisvolle publieke betrokkenheid bij onderzoek*.

¹⁰ Stirling, A. (2008). "Opening up" and "closing down" power, participation, and pluralism in the social appraisal of technology. *Science, Technology, & Human Values*, 33(2), 262-294.

¹¹ Rotman, D., Preece, J., Hammock, J., Procita, K., Hansen, D., Parr, C., ... & Jacobs, D. (2012, February). Dynamic changes in motivation in collaborative citizen-science projects. In *Proceedings of the ACM 2012 conference on computer supported cooperative work* (pp. 217-226).

¹² Roche, J., Bell, L., Galvão, C., Golumbic, Y. N., Kloetzer, L., Knobens, N., ... & Winter, S. (2020). Citizen science, education, and learning: challenges and opportunities. *Frontiers in Sociology*, 5, 613814.

¹³ Sauermaun, H., Vohland, K., Antoniou, V., Balázs, B., Göbel, C., Karatzas, K., ... & Winter, S. (2020). Citizen science and sustainability transitions. *Research Policy*, 49(5), 103978.

Within scholarly research on citizen science and other forms of participatory research, there is fortunately a lot of work being done to identify the creation of framework conditions that can eventually contribute to more equal citizen science.

For motivation, research shows that paying timely attention to different motivations of participants can help volunteers and researchers work together more equally. For example, both groups might start out with their own interests in mind but recognition, appreciation and training when a task or project is finished can soon lead to more collectivist and altruistic motives and thus sustainability of the collaboration.¹⁴

4.1.2 Organisation

Looking at how citizen science is **formally organised and funded**, we see growing attention in various places (Rathenau Institute, 2024). In recent decades, there has been a lot of attention on funding citizen science in Europe.¹⁵

Despite this attention from science and funders, it appears that in practice necessary structures and incentives to implement citizen science are still lacking. Moreover, often the focus is placed on activities and interventions in the first phase of programming research:

For example, funders take great care in drafting call texts, organising matchmaking meetings and setting up evaluation committees to encourage meaningful citizen science. But little thought is given to how citizens collaborate with each other's and with researchers, what can be improved and what lessons can be learned for future projects. Furthermore, it often remains implicit what exactly all stakeholders, even within the same organisation, mean by meaningful citizen science.¹⁶

Even within research projects themselves, it appears that citizens are not always equally involved throughout the process. Too often, citizens and other non-traditional stakeholders are only involved in certain phases of research. For instance, citizens are often involved in data collection or by giving them a role when scientific findings need to be communicated.¹⁷

This is partly linked to the fact that existing funding programmes are not open and flexible enough to allow different participants to participate on equal footing. For instance, funding programmes can have strict topics and methods while citizen science is a process of researching together what works and is relevant. Also, strict role assignments, deadlines and application requirements mean that only institutional players like universities which have the resources and power can organise and participate- in contrast to citizens and other stakeholders who are less organised.¹⁸

¹⁴ Rotman, D., Preece, J., Hammock, J., Procita, K., Hansen, D., Parr, C., ... & Jacobs, D. (2012, February). Dynamic changes in motivation in collaborative citizen-science projects. In *Proceedings of the ACM 2012 conference on computer supported cooperative work* (pp. 217-226).

¹⁵ Macq, H., Tancoigne, É., & Strasser, B. J. (2020). From deliberation to production: public participation in science and technology policies of the European Commission (1998–2019). *Minerva*, 58(4), 489-512.

¹⁶ Rathenau Instituut (2024). Vele handen maken meer dan licht werk – Hoe financiers en kennisinstellingen betekenis kunnen geven aan burgerwetenschap. Den Haag. (Auteurs: Baar, E.J.M., A.M. Scholvinck en J. Deuten), p.5

¹⁷ Stilgoe, J., Lock, S. J., & Wilsdon, J. (2014). Why should we promote public engagement with science? *Public understanding of science*, 23(1), 4-15.

¹⁸ Marschalek, I., Kieslinger, B., Schürz, S., & Schaefer, T. (2023, January). Adapting public funding schemes for participatory research: Managing expectations, overcoming structural constraints. In *Austrian Citizen Science Conference 2022* (p. 27).

Moreover, the focus on temporary programmes and pilots is at risk of remaining one-off experiments that do not structurally contribute to opening up the science system.¹⁹

Fortunately, a lot of work has been done in mapping out possibilities to realise meaningful citizen science. For example, Allf and others show that concrete citizen science projects can be designed volunteer centrally.²⁰ This means paying extra attention to designing the learning process for involved volunteers, more actively guiding their learning process, and paying attention to the involvement of target groups which are not regularly involved and by doing this increasing demographic diversity. It also means investing in the role of project leaders and platforms. Attention should also be paid to the moral, formal and technological frameworks of projects.²¹

We can distinguish six different steps. These need to be taken to develop capacities for citizen science so that everyone who is interested can participate: 1. identifying and involving different actors, 2. assessing existing capacities, 3. identifying wants and needs in a specific setting, 4. developing a mission/vision and action plans, 5. developing websites and other resources, and 6. implementing and evaluating citizen science programmes.²²

The European Commission's Mutual Learning Exercise on Citizen Science Initiatives,²³ led by a group of international experts, shows that investing in 'enabling environments' is crucial. In the final report, the authors summarise research and conclude policy recommendations for citizen science and other forms of participatory research. Based on this meta-analysis, they distinguish between several steps: building national legal frameworks and policies, investing in the further development of institutional policies and culture within knowledge institutions, setting up associations and networks of practical 'hands-on' implementers, designing and maintaining technological data infrastructure and organising social dialogue. Moreover, they call for investing in and experimenting with dedicated funding for citizen science in all these above-mentioned areas.

Funders have a crucial role in creating innovative funding programmes for citizen science, sharing knowledge on best practices and adapting relevant programmes to national and international dimensions.^{24,25}

Recent research also shows that by implementing this, they should pay extra attention to openness and flexibility of funding.²⁶ First, they should make funding available in several successive tranches/stages to not overburden applicants. In addition, they should be more open in the selection of topics and methods to allow citizen scientists to test their chosen methods. Applicants

¹⁹ Cohen, J. B. (2022). Institutionalizing public engagement in research and innovation: Toward the construction of institutional entrepreneurial collectives. *Science and Public Policy*, 49(5), 673-685.

²⁰ Allf, B. C., Cooper, C. B., Larson, L. R., Dunn, R. R., Futch, S. E., Sharova, M., & Cavalier, D. (2022). Citizen science as an ecosystem of engagement: implications for learning and broadening participation. *BioScience*, 72(7), 651-663.

²¹ Wildevuur, S., Dorrestijn, S., Jukema, J., Remmers, G., Wolkorte, R., van Wijk, R. M., & van der Zwart, J. (2023). *Veldboek burgerwetenschap voor gezondheid: Praktijkervaringen in regio Twente*.

²² Hecker, S., Haklay, M., Bowser, A., Makuch, Z., Vogel, J., & Bonn, A. (2018). 19. Capacity building in citizen science. In *Citizen Science: Innovation in Open Science, Society and Policy* (pp. 269-283). University College London.

²³ Gold, M., Haklay, M., Arias, R., Meijer, I., & Radicchi, A. (2022). Mutual learning exercise on citizen science initiatives: policy and practice. Fourth thematic report: enabling environments and sustaining citizen science.

²⁴ COESO. (2022). Fostering Funding for Citizen Science in the Social Sciences and Humanities. https://ibercivis.es/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/COESO-Policy-Brief-Funding_compressed.pdf

²⁵ Bendiscioli, S., Firpo, T., Bravo-Biosca, A., Czibor, E., Garfinkel, M., Stafford, T., ... & Balling, G. V. (2023). The experimental research funder's handbook. https://rori.figshare.com/articles/report/The_experimental_research_funder_s_handbook_final_version_/19459328?file=42259647

²⁶ Marschalek, I., Kieslinger, B., Schürz, S., & Schaefer, T. (2023, January). Adapting public funding schemes for participatory research: Managing expectations, overcoming structural constraints. In *Austrian Citizen Science Conference 2022* (p. 27).

should also be able to switch roles and tasks during the process as participatory research is often a continuously evolving process. Being able to pre-fund/pay non-science partners is also a crucial consideration.

4.1.3 Interaction

There is growing interest in collaboration across domains, with the focus shifting from more science-driven to more community-driven approaches to research.²⁷ In addition, there is increasing attention to the ethical component of collaboration between civic organisations and scientific research.²⁸

In practice, however, citizens are still not always approached equally. They are often not seen as serious and full-fledged research partners, but sometimes only as sensors or data points on the way to the researcher's publications, citations, and funding.²⁹ Moreover, several disadvantaged groups are less often involved, with little attention to differences in timing, culture, and interests.^{30,31}

Besides paying attention to the above differences, training evaluators in assessing this specific type of science is also recommended. Researchers from the Rathenau Institute (2024) point out that working with citizens is not yet a core competency for many researchers. This requires investment in learning and growing. Researchers at Rathenau also point out that research funders could play an even greater role in organising a learning process through targeted training courses and workshops and overarching monitoring of citizen science projects. Some of these elements are already on the agenda of the Dutch Citizen Science Network Netherlands (CS-NL).

4.1.4 Realisation

Citizen science and other types of participatory research can have different forms of impact, during the process and afterwards.³² This impact can manifest itself in different areas, such as scientific impact in the form of new knowledge, impact on the personal and community development of participants and broader socio-ecological and economic impact. Wehn and others distinguish impact in five different domains: society, science and technology, economy, environment and climate, and governance and

²⁷ Soleri, D., Long, J. W., Ramirez-Andreotta, M. D., Eitemiller, R., & Pandya, R. (2016). Finding pathways to more equitable and meaningful public-scientist partnerships. *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*, 1 (1): 9, 1(1).

²⁸ Wiarda, M., Giannelos, K., Schuerz, S., Reber, B., Doorn, N. (2023). Ethics Framework and Guidelines: A guide for research funding organizations implementing participatory activities. DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8089673>

²⁹ Golubic, Y. N., Orr, D., Baram-Tsabari, A., & Fishbain, B. (2017). Between vision and reality: A study of scientists' views on citizen science. *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*, 2(1), 6-6.

³⁰ Pateman, R. M., Dyke, A., & West, S. E. (2021). The diversity of participants in environmental citizen science. *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*.

³¹ Cooper, C. B., Hawn, C. L., Larson, L. R., Parrish, J. K., Bowser, G., Cavalier, D., ... & Wilson, S. (2021). Inclusion in citizen science: The conundrum of rebranding. *Science*, 372(6549), 1386-1388.

³² Mayer, K., Kieslinger, B., & Schäfer, T. (2018, February). Open and participatory citizen social science for evidence-based decision making. In *Austrian Citizen Science Conference* (Vol. 4, pp. 74-77). Frontiers Research Foundation.

politics.³³ Fritz et al. and Fraisl et al. also show what contributions citizen science can make to the SDGs, given sufficient investment.^{34,35}

The question is how much attention is paid to these issues by institutional partners and funders. Many scientists are still judged according to the publish-or-perish model. In discussions around the developments of academic 'Recognition and Rewards', there is fortunately already increasing attention to these dilemmas. Therefore, attention should be paid to provide funding to also integrate the project results and to sustain the cooperation, even after the project has ended.

All this calls for attention to a broader spectrum of quality criteria and success factors³⁶ and asks for various new forms of evaluation of outputs. Recent research by the Rathenau Institute also shows that it is important for funders to make more explicit what exactly is meant by good and meaningful citizen science and to incorporate this into the selection and evaluation criteria's³⁷. According to the researchers, this should make it possible to assess proposals and to monitor and evaluate progress accordingly.

Overall, the Rathenau Institute researchers identified that there is currently still a lot of ambiguity about roles and responsibilities between research funders, policymakers and knowledge institutions. They see this ambiguity specifically in **(seemingly) diffuse division of tasks**: stimulating, facilitating and evaluating citizen science. They recommend that, the Ministry of Education, Culture and Science could initiate the discussion with research funders and knowledge institutions. This conversation should ideally discuss the limitations of current legal frameworks and the goal on how to achieve meaningful citizen science.

4.2 Interviews

In the next chapter, we present our analysis of the results from the interviews using the four parts of our lens on equal collaboration.

4.2.1 Motivation

In the conversations with experts, discussions evolved around their **ambitions** regarding equitable participatory research and the **goals** that such research should contribute to.

Regarding **ambitions**, many of the interviewees note that truly equal participatory research should contribute to **democratisation and sharing of influence** within scientific research. In the words of one science ethicist, this is necessary because "The impact [of science and technology] on society is so great that as a citizen you should also have a say in this. [...] scientific research is too important to be left to scientists alone." Especially when it comes to patients, young people and other

³³ Wehn, U., Gharesifard, M., Ceccaroni, L., Joyce, H., Ajates, R., Woods, S., ... & Wheatland, J. (2021). Impact assessment of citizen science: state of the art and guiding principles for a consolidated approach. *Sustainability Science*, 16(5), 1683-1699.

³⁴ Fritz, S., See, L., Carlson, T., Haklay, M., Oliver, J. L., Fraisl, D., ... & West, S. (2019). Citizen science and the United Nations sustainable development goals. *Nature Sustainability*, 2(10), 922-930.

³⁵ Fraisl, D., Campbell, J., See, L., Wehn, U., Wardlaw, J., Gold, M., ... & Fritz, S. (2020). Mapping citizen science contributions to the UN sustainable development goals. *Sustainability Science*, 15, 1735-1751.

³⁶ Gold, M. (2020). Quality & Success Factors for Citizen Science based on the ECSA 10 Principles. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10670875>

³⁷ Rathenau Instituut (2024). Vele handen maken meer dan licht werk – Hoe financiers en kennisinstellingen betekenis kunnen geven aan burgerwetenschap. Den Haag. (Auteurs: Baar, E.J.M., A.M. Scholvinck en J. Deuten)

vulnerable or marginalised groups, it is important to act on the motto "nothing about us, without us", says a transdisciplinary researcher. This revolves around patients and citizens and "letting their actions really be at the heart of scientific knowledge". This, according to a well-known voice in the Dutch citizen science domain, requires a "fundamental democratic openness to other kinds of perspectives" and "the perspective of that we are all knowledge producers. [We are] all homo investigans. [...] That is not reserved for people who have special training for that". Many of the interviewees conclude that this means that truly meaningful engagement must also lead to "real power for citizens". As one UK research funder puts it, "it's about valuing different partners and recognising what they bring to the table. [...] Making sure that power and money are equally distributed. It's about democratising things."

This also means approaching citizens not only as potential data points or data collectors for a research institution's project. In fact, it is not just about involving citizens in scientific research but rather approaching citizens as co-researchers and experts in 'real life'. One UK research funder therefore sees an important task for themselves in removing barriers so that research and innovation become a "shared endeavour", working on "research that is important to certain parts of society and they are involved and owners of it. To make sure that people don't just feel like they just have information extracted from them". This requires recognising and valuing citizens and other stakeholders as equal collaboration partners. As one Austrian research funder sums up nicely: "In my ideal citizen science world researchers come to take the know-how, honour this and say: 'you are the experts'. It's about trying to involve them in an honourable way, valuing their expertise and seeing them as real partners".

A third theme that often recurs when it comes to ambitions, is **the importance of building ecosystems around participatory research**. One Dutch research funder who has worked extensively on funding participatory youth research sees the time and effort she puts into it as "helping to create a movement" in which such forms of research can become the norm. That it does not just take place at the "edges" of a university or research institution but becomes more normative. Building a movement sometimes feels bumpy for those involved, but the aforementioned research funder also experiences that "everyone finds what we have done super interesting and there is a lot of enthusiasm for it. So, it sparks something: this is fun and innovative, and this is something that should be happening more. You also receive recognition and energy." At the same time, a well-known researcher from the citizen science field in the Netherlands notes that there is also a lot already going on in practice and that we should watch out for a "shiny new things bias". For her, building ecosystems is therefore about connecting existing examples in neighbourhoods, scaling them up so that together, all these 'pearls' form a stronger and more cohesive 'string'.

The **goals** equal partnership projects in citizen science can pursue, can also be plotted on a horizontal and vertical axis. In the words of a citizen scientist:

My plea is to always keep the potential of citizen science as broad as possible: the horizontal axis ranging from citizen-driven to scientist-driven, and the vertical axis from individually motivated, to collectively motivated. For me, citizen science can very well be driven purely by scientists for general goals, if it is clear what the role of the citizen is. I often see things being presented as citizen science, while it's not clear what the citizen's role is.

The goals may also **differ per domain and target group**. Within research on healthy living environments, for example, residents of a given municipality participate out of intrinsic motivation. This could be to express their dissatisfaction with an existing situation or because they "think green is important and want to contribute to it". Thereby, according to one interviewed researcher, it is important that there is not only a focus on increasing awareness about sustainability but also a real improvement in the quality of the natural and living environment. In the social domain, for example, participatory research can help break down stigmas about marginalised groups. Someone who conducts participatory research with homeless people describes it as a way of giving them a voice in debates that are often held about them but rarely with them. In the health domain, it can be about putting people more in control by empowering them to do "baseline research" and examine their own bodies and health.

Interestingly, many of the experts-by-experience mention **reciprocity between researchers and citizens as an important goal** for mutual partnership citizen science projects. An Austrian research funder therefore states that the first goal of mutual partnership citizen science projects should be to collaborate with citizens in the best possible way and enable them through training to influence the project design. This also requires clarity in defining the goals of a research project. One researcher describes this as follows:

The question is: what is the goal? Do you invite them to participate in your process? Or do you invite them to design a process together? Or do you invite them to test what you came up with in your research? That gets mixed up quite often.

Two researchers who work a lot with city residents stress that the **questions should be community-driven** or at least drafted together with the neighbourhood. A Dutch researcher stresses that for true equality, it is important **to start "from the target group: who is it and then go to where they are. Very much listening to what is going on, regardless of all the other interests and parties pulling at you. [...] And then from scratch look at how you can contribute to change [and] then gradually start doing it."** As one UK research funder also says: "Sometimes what is interesting for researchers may not be the critical issue." Ultimately, it is also about doing this kind of innovative form of science together "with your feet in the clay. Show it, do it together, then it will capture the imagination".

4.2.2 Organisation

During the in-depth interviews, we also discussed the current and needed organisation of mutual partnership participatory research processes and support/funding for this.

In the current situation, stakeholders encounter several **barriers that lead to unequal collaborations**. First, there is a lot of **competition for existing research grants**. Within this context, structural funding for citizen scientists "turns out to be incredibly tough. We must twist oneself into knots to receive a grant. We almost have to give up our identity because NWO is very strict with eligible institutions." As a result, citizen scientists are still highly dependent on "rare gems" within the research system—exceptional individuals who can act as *bridge-builders*—since citizen scientists themselves are often not permitted to apply for funding.

Many interviewees particularly mention the **lack of possibilities to reimburse expenses** for citizens, patients, artists and people receiving social benefits, for example. It is quite difficult to compensate people without knowing in advance exactly what to compensate for (e.g. for babysitting costs or travel expenses). This leads to a lot of frustration also on the side of funders themselves: "you want to establish something more structural, and yet you still deal with gift vouchers".

This is linked to the fact that research funders are bound to existing laws, regulations and procedures. Thus, a funder cannot just "gradually change the rules of the game to create a just level playing field within regulatory frameworks. [...] As a result, you can't gradually change the procedures". A UK research funder recognises this but notes that this can also lead to additional exclusion of parties with fewer resources to prepare an application: "It's understandable that you have these rigid processes in place, but it needs to be proportionate."

The disparity is also in the **funding of materials used for research**: "funders fund mega-computers but not consumer applications or websites like *waarnemingen.nl*". They also do not fund the "huge pre-investment" it takes to build **connections and relationships** with residents of a particular neighbourhood or district. Thus, "support platforms" and building relationships are less recognised and valued in comparison to conducting the scientific research. But not only research funders experience barriers. **Universities themselves have rules** about who they pay for what kind of work. With all the contract requirements

involved, it is difficult to properly compensate citizens for their efforts. Ethical review committees can also challenge citizen science projects if they are not familiar with participatory research: "*Views of what constitutes good research and ethics then get mixed up and then it becomes impossible.*"

Against these barriers, there are many examples of **best practices** for organising and funding equal collaborations. For example, some researchers decide in consultation with patients what is a good reimbursement model. Others point to the Culture Fund as a good example for a fund with an ongoing open call which is flexible enough to leave room for various outcomes. When we asked interviewees what **forms of support** would be needed for equal participatory research, several options are mentioned. For example, there is an almost unanimous call for **appreciating voluntary work** for citizens, patients and, for example, artists who participate in research. According to a municipal employee who is actively involved in citizen science, this could include **reimbursing travel expenses, babysitting costs and other opportunity costs**. Especially for the "*unusual suspects because they have to make extra efforts to find physical and psychological space for participating. [...] They can't participate if you don't meet their needs. We often talk about what do you want to see reimbursed? Taking children to daycare, charging equipment, free coffee, et cetera?*" It also calls for more '**creation budget**'. This is material costs for building something concrete with each other, as a form of interaction that goes further than just conversations, interviews and other spoken forms of interactions.

Funders have a particular role to play here, by **funding both research from institutions and research from people not affiliated with such institutions**. In addition, funders can provide **guidelines and advice** on how the scientists with a grant can share their budgets with citizens and other stakeholders. This also requires developing internal capacities, according to the UK research funder:

There's lots of problems around state public support etc. but we're talking about what we do as a funder. People will do it out of the kindness of their heart but are also looking at funders. How are we supporting our colleagues running those funding calls? How do we support them to think about the development of projects and the people that they are funding? That differs per discipline and what's being asked of the researchers and public, but there are various touchpoints where we can open up.

In this context, a Dutch research funder that funds participatory youth research also talks about creating **practical guidance documents and tools** for funding young people who participate in research. But often no real solution has been found yet.

Looking at suitable **budget requirements** and other requirements for support, many stakeholders advocate for **staged funding** in which there is enough time and space for setting up and strengthening relationships. This could start with matching workshops in which initial ideas are outlined, following co-creation workshops in which participants are paid to jointly develop a plan with professional scientists, and lastly the option to jointly develop a proposal. UKRI is also experimenting with ways to **formalise the roles of public contributors or public engagement experts** in their processes and applications, so that funding is specifically earmarked for their roles too. One participatory researcher who has authored several citizen science articles warns not to place too much responsibility on citizens who cannot fall back on professional organisations: "*you, for example, can also have the problem of liability: you need to prevent that people go bankrupt: if the project is a failure and if citizens apply for the money and don't have institutional backings, it may overburden them.*"

This is another reason why some interviewees advocate for funding **short-term pilots and 6-12-month projects to 'try things out'**. Short-term pilots can also include workshops, scientists speaking in schools, or small competitions where a prize can be won for further development of ideas around citizen science. This kind of funding also helps to involve people who do not normally participate. In this context, people also advocate for issuing **kick-off and sustaining grants**. A citizen scientist describes, "*that is*

also nicer for small civil society organisations in terms of accountability pressure. Smaller calls with modest budgets with less pressure on accountability."

Everyone we spoke to agrees that **small kick-off grants are not enough for equal long-term collaborations**. Instead, these need time to grow and mature. A participatory researcher also gives an interesting example of how this has worked in practice in Malta:

[for example there is] a project on biodiversity monitoring that I am mentoring. It came out of pollinator research on bees. It was too much for them to do at the time and [the sustaining grant] was really helpful in reviving [the project]. The person working on this is now working to institutionalize the citizen science community in Malta. The environmental research agency needs to collect data on biodiversity and for them she and her network are a godsend. They also get money from the environmental research agency to fund it further. That was a good example of how much impact you can get with a real small grant.

Precisely because **mutual partnership collaborations call for building longer-term relationships, interviewees advocate for funding which also runs longer**. A good example of this is the Sparkling Science programme in Austria, which focuses on establishing equal collaborations between scientists and schools/pupils. Here, a duration of two to three years was chosen after trying out different formats. And by building these relationships, the end of funding also does not have to mean the end of the partnership: *"It helps because we have research organisations that have good partnerships with the schools. That is the thing we wanted to reach: bring science and schools together, even if we don't fund them the whole time."* This requires **networking and training support** for those involved (see chapter Interaction for more on this).

The UK research funder UKRI describes how they are also **experimenting with funding designed to build partnerships**: *"With the citizen science collaborations we gave them funding to explore a partnership. For example, looking at medical research: if you have an expectation that people will be involved as patients, you can give funding to establish partnerships pre-research"*. Especially with marginalised communities, he says: *"That particularly needs to be done with underrepresented communities who need time to trust who have experienced previous extractive practices."* He stresses the importance of **time and attention** beyond six months or a year. This also means **aftercare** after temporary funding ends: *"If you want equitable relationships, you need time. There is value in six months if you tag along with more funding after. But you need to make sure that you do not perpetuate that people feel they are picked up and dropped down."* But the time horizon does sometimes differ by target group. For example, a research funder working with young people describes that they often find a year as very long.

A good alternative is to work with **longer-term trajectories in which an iteration is done yearly**. One participation expert describes that he likes to experiment with four-year projects in which the same cycle of involving people, co-creating things together and then delivering intermediate products is done every year. At the end, the result is a wider community of stakeholders who also want to move forward themselves. It could also be an option to make look for additional, alternative sources of funding a part of the research process. This can be facilitated both by research funders who then organise more funding for concrete products like measurement apps and by alternative funders who are more focused on market and app development.

When asked about **assessment criteria** for funding equal partnership participatory research projects, interviewees emphasised several points. First, projects should pay attention to which target groups they involve. According to the UK research funder UKRI, they also pay particular attention to **how a project defines the target group, how they intend to establish a relationship with the group, and which voice the target group will have in the design and implementation of a project**: *"One of the things that we are constantly looking at is how it is responsive. And how they approach the relationship with the public. You need to make sure that you engage with people who have relevant knowledge and expertise. Are the right people in the room? [...] How*

equal are the voices in the room? [...] Is it a little bit about real-world problems?" If the target group is not well defined, if citizens or other non-traditional stakeholders are not given a clear equal role, or if it does not address real problems, no funding is provided.

A Dutch research funder also explicitly tests *"whether the right collaboration partners are present and what the budget distribution is like. You have to be careful that it does not become a tick box."* In Austria, a funder also provides more funding for projects that work with *"underserved schools or schools somewhere in the valley. We think it very important that funding organizations put emphasis on this: the research landscape but also the school landscape have hotspots or blind spots and try to reach them. This is harder and costs more in terms of communication and training for pupils and researchers."*

A second aspect is **sufficient ways to engage different audiences**: *"You need [...] to allow different entrance points and methods. Non-verbal methods for example"*. According to one researcher, research also shows that if attention is paid to criteria of diversity, equality as well as a good definition of vulnerable target groups in the text of calls, this has a significant effect on how projects are set up. Making grant applications more accessible can also help in this respect.

However, this does not mean that everything should be completely fixed during the process. Citizen science and other forms of participatory research also require flexibility and adaptive capacity during the project's length to be flexible to respond to the needs of the target group(s). In Austria, the situation is such that: *"They have their goals, but it is not always possible to reach the goals in the ways in which you thought it would work. [...] If projects want to change during the process based on [pupil's needs] we allow them to do it. Because in citizen science we know it needs to be done and give them the possibility to do this."*

Furthermore, everyone unanimously agrees that a **clear and plausible objective and impact strategy and a transparent division of tasks, roles and responsibilities are necessary for equal collaboration**: *"Often the latter are not clear. Expectation management, the decision-making process and the planning of effort, time and resources are not to be underestimated"*. To help selecting equal partnership projects, attention needs to be given to potential ethical risks and overseeing mitigation strategies, as well as attention to how failure is handled and to how to learn which assessment criteria works. However, attention on ethics must be carefully balanced against the impact on participation. One participatory researcher provides the example that she sometimes works with target groups such as low-literate parents or homeless people who have a fear of forms. Can you obtain the consent of these people in other ways through voice memos, for example: *"If you go back to the essence of why such a protocol is [for data collection and processing] set up, you can design it more inclusively, rather than having to follow the protocol exactly?"*

Overall, interviewees also note that change is needed in **what is recognised and valued as success within scientific research**: *"we need to be reframing the standard indicators for success: not just publish-or-perish [...] it is really important to consider how scientific expertise is framed and how goals are defined"*. This also requires attention to the equal involvement of citizens and non-traditional stakeholders during performance and assessment interviews and recruitment and selection interviews at knowledge institutions. In doing so, attention should be paid to differences between domains and types of research.

4.2.3 Interaction

This last point also touches on how informal interaction is currently organised and the **current culture of collaboration within research**. This is partly influenced by **power differences between stakeholders**. In Britain, for instance, there is a long history of researchers mainly gathering data that further emphasises inequalities: *"We know that there are certain sections of society who have a lot of research about them done but historically they don't hear about the impact of the research and don't see it"*. The situation also occurs in the Netherlands where citizens are sometimes over asked from researchers. This is the case in the Afrikaander neighbourhood in Rotterdam, where residents *"went completely crazy with all the researchers wanting all sorts of things from them"*. Differences can also be more subtle and related to the characteristics of the specific target group. In youth

research, for instance, young people themselves cannot apply for research. They can ask for salary for their involvement in a project, but they often have no experience with salary negotiations.

At a deeper level, it is also about **prejudices that different groups can have about each other** that can hinder equal partnership collaborations. Within traditional research circles, different images about what citizens and other non-traditional stakeholders can bring to research exist. The interviewed science ethicist indicates that in his *"working life he has met a lot of people in the biotechnology world, and I hear a lot of complaining about citizens."* Citizens can also feel inferior to scientists. According to one citizen scientist, this also has to do with views and questions about whether citizens have competences and fear of enabling 'pseudoscience': *"In particular, professionals who are not familiar with it and occasionally speak to patients in the waiting room are afraid they will support pseudoscience if we enable this."* This is certainly not an exclusively Dutch phenomenon. In Austria, a research funder says she also had to face prejudice: *"When we started in 2007 people said: you are crazy, [pupils] cannot be researchers."* A municipal employee notes that citizens do not want to *"share data with the municipality just like that. [...] People no longer trust the government"* or *"find universities scary"*.

The discussion above is also linked to a **lack of a sustainable relationships between universities and local residents**. This in turn leads to short-term wishful thinking aimed at quick solutions from which mainly researchers benefit. For example, someone came up with the idea that residents could take surveys of fellow residents in the neighbourhood via an employment agency. But many residents did not aspire a career as researcher at all. The deeper problem, one of the interviewees involved analyses, is again linked to the publication-oriented scientific system and *"the unwillingness to recognise this research as research. [...] Researchers then also think I have to produce all these papers, and now I also have to spend time in the neighbourhood!"*

Involving citizens on a more equal footing is possible if the threshold for participation is lowered. This can be done, for instance, by organising neighbourhood gatherings or by starting the conversation via community workers or neighbourhood workers, who can be reimbursed for this. It is also possible by involving young people through schools. A municipal employee describes: *"Children can think along perfectly, they are the citizens of the future. If we offer children things on a platter, it stays with them. The schools are very enthusiastic. In spring, we are going to offer a climate suitcase with assignments and tools so they can take measurements and analyse them on the playground. [...] Hopefully those children can excite their parents."* Ultimately, she says, it is also about getting people out of their isolation. Organising meetings in community centres with food and drinks and organising mini events make it fun and attractive to join and to have a conversation about what people need to participate in participatory research.

Recognising and valuing such participation does not always have to be monetary. It can be achieved through making room in the proposal for collaborating on a journal article or other creative tasks. Or about mandating that researchers or students first volunteer in a particular context before talking about their research to people in the neighbourhood.

The Austrian research funder indicates that research funders can also manage this, by including **budget, space and time for a learning process** in which attention is paid to equal partnerships. In Britain, they also see it as their core task as research funders to spark the conversation about any form of support for citizen science: *"Being a catalyst for those conversations helps us to get a feel for what we do in research and public organisations, and what they do with this work."* Through publishing essays on these topics, they further fuel the debate on barriers and opportunities for equal partnerships in participatory research.

But support can also take other forms. Within participatory research projects, for example, participants are experimenting with **setting up an agreement for equal collaboration**, in which they state what their own limits and needs are for participation and how they will be compensated. All project members must sign this agreement. Furthermore, it is also important to leave things open for the target group and be **more empathic about their needs**. This also means being approachable as a funder, and: *"also much more aftercare: that you pay attention to that. The warmer side is important, not just sending a letter of procedure."*

What is also often mentioned is investing into soft skills among citizens and non-traditional stakeholders as well as scientists through **training, networking events, mutual learning opportunities and knowledge sharing**. Funders can also play a guiding role in this. For example, interviewees describe the crucial importance of training for skills to facilitate groups, ethics in participation and data management. The Austrian research funder also stresses that they ask all project leaders from previous projects to talk with peers about their previous experiences and lessons learned. This way, they create a continuous learning process, even after the projects have ended.

At a more fundamental level, it is also about **daring to share power** with citizens and other non-traditional stakeholders. It is about daring to share more "true decision-making power" from the start. According to a Dutch research funder, that means bringing together the knowledge goal of researchers and the goal for change of a community group. The UK research funder UKRI shares how they look at this: "It's also getting away from a paternalistic approach of the funder and academic institution deciding what is good. How can we make everything more co-productive already at the funding level? How can we make our colleagues within funding more comfortable in that?" Sharing influence is then at both programme and project level. An Austrian research funder states, "If you do a citizen science project and you work together with pupils, their interest should also come into the project design." This way of funding sometimes seems scary to traditionally trained funders and researchers, because can one trust that it leads to good science? A science ethicist who has talked a lot with citizens and organised a lot of participation notes that "citizens who are treated as legitimate holders of knowledge are also going to behave that way."

Even within **evaluation committees**, this requires selecting the right people and **further developing their skills and expertise to discuss and evaluate research proposals** together with people from other disciplines and backgrounds. First, this requires that they themselves have well-developed communication skills and can be open to alternative views and experiences. It also requires people who understand what transdisciplinary research is and who have knowledge of the specific methods proposed. Understanding participation, for example, does not yet mean that someone also understands what citizen science means.

Involving non-academic target groups in the assessment of proposals is also necessary to bring equal relationships one step closer. For example, the Austrian funder indicates that it also asks school representatives in the assessment committee, precisely to include the target group's perspective: "Is it interesting for the schools and is it not just collecting data?" They also organise a scientific advisory board that checks the overall quality of the assessments and can intervene in case of disputes.

Perhaps inherent to a transdisciplinary assessment committee is the fact that discussions could feel uncomfortable. Therefore, much attention needs to be paid to **creating the right conditions for a good and open conversation**. An interviewee from the UK research funder UKRI notes that "organising diversity" means bringing the committee together ahead of time so that they can jointly discuss the guidelines for their conversations. This is to avoid that citizens are treated as inferior participants in the assessment committee meetings. An interviewee from a Dutch funder also has good experiences with this: "I had them come together beforehand to reflect upon their own judgements with young people. That did give them extra security and confidence even though they had already done a good job."

Furthermore, a **different attitude from funders** is also needed. As one participation expert describes it, "it comes back to attitude: to what extent do people with privileges really dare to engage to make the unheard voices audible?" This also requires funders to consider the needs of target groups and "to open up to where their needs lie, otherwise you will lose them. You always must be aware of: what is my perspective and what are my own blind spots?". This can also mean to experiment with relationships. For example, a Dutch research funder experimented with different language:

Initially, we said: young people in the lead. It then becomes very clear that the issue must come from them. The researchers then must address it. So that is also a change of perspective, where we first talked to the young people for

three months: What do you want? What is your need? So that researchers are not just involving citizens but that the voice of young people is the starting point.

At the same time, this means that funders have the **responsibility to be transparent** about what is and what is not possible within the existing legal frameworks. Or, if these are too tight, to initiate the discussion on this at a higher policy level.

4.2.4 Realisation

Finally, during the interviews, we asked about **possible outcomes of citizen science and other forms of participatory research**. Someone with extensive experience as a participatory researcher summed it up:

It really depends on the goals of the project. Citizen science can deliver better science because you can get better evidence from the lived experience of people, and there are more perspectives involved. This can lead to better solutions and better implementation because of their involvement already during the process. It can also lead to more trust. But it can also backfire which will result in less trust. It can also have an educational perspective and lead to the development of critical thinking skills.

Involving citizens and other non-traditional stakeholders can help deepen and broaden **conversations about possible solutions for complex societal challenges**. Many interviewees recognise that involving citizens can help collect more data. Even with inexpensive equipment, good research can be done in this way on, for example tracking temperature, humidity, air quality and particulate matter.

Involving citizens can therefore also contribute to **other types of outcomes, which are more focused on social cohesion**, in the form of growing mutual understanding between participants and institutions. By working with them on an equal footing, citizens can also gain more confidence in institutions when they value their input. Their involvement in research and through conversations can also provide insight into "*types of arguments and sentiments that need to be addressed*" in research and development. A researcher points out that involving citizens and other stakeholders for longer can also contribute to a better understanding of the long-term impact: "*contributing to a society that cares, rather than focusing on quick fixes*".

A citizen scientist notes that it is **important for projects to not try to tick all the boxes**: "*Ideally, in a project both the researcher and citizen get something out of it, as an individual and for the broader public. [...] I would advise against aiming for projects that tick all the boxes. That quickly becomes very generic.*" He also indicates that, with that freedom scientific research can evolve from a "*claims factory to a hypothesis factory*".

It is important to keep in mind that the **output is also meaningful to non-scientists**. This implies that scientific publications should not be seen as the standard product in participatory research. There should be room for alternative forms of output, such as public and accessible forms of communication like e.g. a magazine for a broad target group or interventions like community building or a new sustainability institution. "*What I think is of immense value is that you can invest in communities and community-building in an effective way. This ties into the other aspect: you can set up things like environmental stewardships in which citizens feel responsible for taking care of their environment*".

A prerequisite for better outcomes and results from participatory research is a **good learning process**. Ultimately, many interviewees say that good participatory research processes should not be seen as separate interventions, but rather as **interventions that are part of a larger learning process**. This also calls for other forms of monitoring and evaluation such as

reflexive monitoring that are more adapted to the fact that projects and programmes can change during their lifetime based on participants' ideas.

It also requires that **research funders are flexible and dare to experiment**. In Austria, they are already successfully experimenting by undergoing a continuous review process to evaluate if interventions are successful: "*We check what aims or results they want to achieve and what the research questions are. If they change their way one of our first questions is: is it possible with the change that you get better answers to your questions?*" In the Netherlands, a research funder also experimented with alternative forms of funding by simultaneously linking it to a learning process. This included explicit funding for intervention sessions and meetings to reflect on the collaboration between the researchers and the people from outside of academia.

4.2.5 *Additional tips for funding equitable participatory research*

Finally, we asked the experience experts to share insights which NWO could use to create a funding programme for equal partnership citizen science research and other forms of participatory research. One citizen scientist recommended looking at how funding is organised in the cultural sector.

You must have money for amateur orchestras as well as for amateur scientists. The idea is that we all can do research, that you honour that and make budgets available for all kinds of levels. That is what we need. Don't just fund the symphony orchestra but also the smaller orchestras. This is also based on the assumption that grassroots sport is necessary to fund top-level sport.

An interviewee from the Austrian research funder stresses that **publicly funded outputs** such as trainings and guidelines **should be made publicly available** and that further efforts could be made to support networking through conferences and other meetings. A participatory researcher also advocates for funding citizen scientists to run or participate in workshops.

An interviewee from the UK research funder UKRI underlines the **importance of collaboration between research funders, knowledge institutions and grassroots movements** that are already pioneering with equal collaborations in research practice. This, he says, also requires additional investment in communities that have traditionally lacked access to knowledge:

We currently talk more about equity than equality because there are sections of society that are not engaging, and we need to invest in those communities. So that's why we focus more on that than equality. It's not about everyone having the opportunity but making sure that those who need it get the additional support. There are communities who constantly had extractive practice and who do not feel research is for them. So that's something that you need to actively address rather than just being open.

According to him, this also requires **research funders who dare to build and connect coalitions both internally and externally**. In the words of one science ethicist: "*Is NWO the referee? They are also on the playing field.*" An interviewee from a Dutch research funder advocates for creating room for experimentation, working on new forms of research funding with a focus on core values. As far as she is concerned, "*daring more and doing more.*"

4.2.6 *Best practices in The Netherlands and abroad*

Several **good examples** also came up during the interviews that can be used to inspire or further develop funding for equal partnerships in participatory research.

At **local and regional level**, there are several collaborations between citizen scientists and researchers such as, for example, *Wijkwijjs* in Rotterdam ³⁸, Citizen Science Hub Twente³⁹, Life Critical in Dordrecht⁴⁰ or *Samen Meten* Utrecht that already do a lot of knowledge sharing and networking.⁴¹ Citizen scientists in the Netherlands have also been able to join forces on a national level through the Citizen Science Network Netherlands (CS-NL) which also received support from Open Science NL. CS-NL supports resource sharing.⁴² The Self Research Network Netherlands (ZONN) already supports different patient researchers and publishes about preconditions for equal partnership citizen science in health research.⁴³

NWO's National Research Agenda (NWA) is a well-known initiative, where questions from citizens are matched with scientists who want to do research on them.⁴⁴ Within the NWA, research is currently being conducted on how citizen science is currently being implemented in ongoing funded projects and the challenges and positive aspects are that participants experience. ZonMw has recently partnered with the Heart Foundation in funding citizen science research on heart conditions. In 2022, ZonMw funded a participatory learning network on participatory youth research ⁴⁵ which has drawn up guidelines and recommendations for equal collaboration with young people.⁴⁶

In Flanders, Scivil, a knowledge centre for citizen science, is working on knowledge development and networking, resulting in an extensive overview of guides and manuals for citizen science.⁴⁷ In Germany, the *Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung* pays attention to embedding citizen science in the research ecosystem.⁴⁸ Over the past few years, UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) has invested heavily into funding equal partnerships in participatory research, through for example Citizen Science Exploration Grants where 28 projects received funding on the condition that they share their experiences in order to further develop funding in this area. This led to several useful insights⁴⁹ and recommendations⁵⁰ and follow-up research through so-called Citizen Science Collaboration Grants.⁵¹ In addition, several scoping studies, evaluations and reports have been released in the last few years. Furthermore, networks and projects have been launched that can provide more insight into how to practice and fund equal partnership participatory research.⁵²⁵³⁵⁴ The *Ideas Fund* and the *Citizen science for food standards* are also examples of flagship initiatives.⁵⁵⁵⁶

³⁸ <https://www.eur.nl/onderzoek/onderzoeksprogrammas/vcc-proiectpagina/wijkonderzoekscollectief>

³⁹ <https://www.utwente.nl/nl/designlab/citizen-science/>

⁴⁰ <https://groenblauwdordrecht.nl/nieuws/wielwijk-proeftuin-tegen-klimaatverandering/>

⁴¹ <https://samenmetenutrecht.nl/samen-meten-utrecht/>

⁴² <https://citizenscience.nl/>

⁴³ <https://zelfonderzoeknetwerk.nl/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/2024-Remmers-et-al-CS-for-Health-enabling-factors-CSTP.pdf>

⁴⁴ <https://wetenschapsagenda.nl/over-ons>

⁴⁵ <https://projecten.zonmw.nl/nl/project/leernetwerk-participatief-jeugdonderzoek>

⁴⁶ https://www.zonmw.nl/sites/zonmw/files/2023-12/019_093_JEUGDPARTICIPATIE_2023_WEB_DEF.pdf

⁴⁷ <https://www.scivil.be/book/gidsen-en-handleidingen>

⁴⁸ https://www.bmbf.de/DE/Forschung/Gesellschaft/Beteiligungdergesellschaft/CitizenScience/citizenscience_node.html

⁴⁹ <https://www.youngfoundation.org/our-work/publications/experiences-of-citizen-science/>

⁵⁰ <https://youngfoundation.b-cdn.net/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/CSEG-report-final-.pdf?x83233>

⁵¹ <https://www.youngfoundation.org/institute-for-community-studies/our-work/citizen-science/about-the-programme/>

⁵² <https://www.youngfoundation.org/our-work/publications/an-equitable-future-for-research-and-innovation/>

⁵³ <https://www.youngfoundation.org/our-work/publications/local-knowledge-national-potential/>

⁵⁴ <https://www.youngfoundation.org/insights/news/new-funding-will-help-put-communities-at-the-heart-of-research/>

⁵⁵ <https://theideasfund.org/>

⁵⁶ <https://www.food.gov.uk/research/research-projects/citizen-science-for-food-standards-challenges-programme-review>

In Austria there is the Sparkling Science 2.0 programme where more than 120,000 citizens (of which the vast majority is a student) teamed up with more than 6,000 researchers and 5,000 teachers to conduct joint and equal research on their living environment.⁵⁷ As of 2021, €21 million has already been invested in this initiative by the Austrian government.

At **European** level, the European Citizen Science Association has a working group on *Empowerment, inclusiveness and equity* in which knowledge is shared on equal partnership collaboration.⁵⁸ The European Commission also funded two Mutual Learning Exercises (MLE), one on Citizen Science and one on Public Engagement in research & innovation with many relevant outputs for funders and policymakers.⁵⁹⁶⁰ In addition, the IMPETUS and INCENTIVE projects experimented with ways to fund and support equal partnership citizen science.⁶¹⁶²

⁵⁷ <https://oead.at/en/study-research-teaching/citizen-science/sparkling-science>

⁵⁸ <https://www.ecsa.ngo/working-groups/empowerment-inclusiveness-equity/>

⁵⁹ <https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/statistics/policy-support-facility/psf-challenge/mutual-learning-exercise-citizen-science-initiatives-policy-and-practice>

⁶⁰ <https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/statistics/policy-support-facility/psf-challenge/mutual-learning-exercise-public-engagement-ri>

⁶¹ <https://impetus4cs.eu/>

⁶² <https://incentive-project.eu/>

5. Interim conclusion

Despite the current challenges in equal partnerships in participatory research, there is a lot of interest in this subject in the Netherlands and abroad. In this interim report, based on a desk review and interviews with 15 experts from the Netherlands and abroad, we have tried to find answers to the following question:

What are the preconditions for equal partnership collaborations of citizens (organisations) and researchers in research projects?

Using our lens, we found that equal collaboration in participatory research requires attention to **four aspects: motivation, organisation, interaction and realisation.**

The results from the desk research and the interviews provide several starting points for NWO to design funding programmes to support equal partnership collaborations in participatory research. For example, by focusing on the **motivations of citizens and other non-traditional stakeholders** and by already sharing the influence already during project design and decision-making, NWO can contribute to equal partnership collaboration. By considering **phased funding possibilities**, including temporary, short-term pilots and sustaining grants and more long-term funding, NWO can contribute to sustainable community building between citizens and researchers. Reimbursing travel and other costs such as childcare can also contribute to engaging different target groups, just as flexible programmes with enough room for adjustments.

This interim report also shows that many prejudices still exist between citizens, researchers and governmental officials. **Investing in networking, training, creating guidelines and boosting easy ways of collaboration** could all help to address these prejudices and thus contribute to better equal partnership collaborations. Investing in the **skills and expertise of assessment committee members** can also help. The paper contains concrete recommendations on how to tackle this.

In conclusion, this interim report shows that citizen science and other forms of participatory research may **produce different outcomes.** These can range from more democratic and better research to better solutions and more trust in scientific research. This, however, requires creating **a learning process and space for experimenting with new forms of funding.**

In the next social lab meetings, we will use these outcomes to work with practitioners to develop community-supported recommendations for funding equal partnerships in participatory research. In a subsequent report, we will discuss the outcomes and results of this.

Annex 1: List of interviewees

Organisation	Role
Centre for Ethics and Health	Senior researcher
Utrecht School of the Arts	Policy and grant advisor for practice-based research
Municipality of Dordrecht	Project manager
ZSI	Senior researchers and project leaders
My Data Our Health	Director
OeAD	Programme manager
UKRI	Public engagement lead
Utrecht School of the Arts	Visual artist and researcher
DesignLab Twente	Director
Bureau Ruimtekoers	Participatory designer
ZonMw	Programme manager
Leiden University	Citizen science lead
Erasmus University Rotterdam	PhD researcher
University of Delft	Innovation and impact specialist

Werken met TwynstraGudde betekent samen maatschappelijke transitie werkend krijgen. Met advies, management en opleidingen helpen we mensen en organisaties bij duurzame veranderingen. Denk aan energie en klimaat, wonen, veiligheid, landbouw, mobiliteit, zorg en onderwijs. Onze kracht ligt in daadkracht. In het creëren van oplossingen die werkbaar zijn én werkbaar blijven. Samen met onze opdrachtgevers - en alle belanghebbenden daaromheen - werken we aan een samenleving die schoon, veilig, gezond en weerbaar is. Zo maken we blijvend impact op morgen.